

FREQUENCY OF CORONARY ARTERY DISEASE IN TYPE 2 DIABETES MELLITUS PATIENTS

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Abstract

Objective:

The objective of this study was to determine the frequency of coronary artery disease in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus and to compare its frequency between patients with controlled and uncontrolled diabetes.

Study Design:

Descriptive cross-sectional study.

Place and Duration of Study:

This study was conducted in the Department of Medicine, Provincial Headquarter Hospital Gilgit, from 22th Feb 2025 to 15th June 2025.

Methodology:

A total of 83 patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus aged between 30 and 70 years who presented with chest pain were included in the study. Patients were selected by non-probability consecutive sampling. Glycemic control was assessed using HbA1c levels and patients were classified as controlled or uncontrolled diabetes. Coronary artery disease was diagnosed on the basis of clinical presentation, electrocardiographic changes and raised cardiac troponin I levels. All data were recorded on a predesigned proforma. Data entry and analysis was done using SPSS version 25. Mean and standard deviation were calculated for quantitative variables while frequencies and percentages were calculated for categorical variables. Comparison of coronary artery disease between controlled and uncontrolled diabetes was done using chi square test and a p value of less than or equal to 0.05 was taken as statistically significant.

Results:

Out of 83 patients, coronary artery disease was found in 29 patients which makes a frequency of 34.9 percent. Coronary artery disease was more commonly observed in patients with uncontrolled type 2 diabetes mellitus as compared to those with controlled diabetes. Among uncontrolled patients, 45.2 percent had coronary artery disease while only 18.2 percent of controlled patients were affected and this difference was statistically significant. Increasing age, longer duration of diabetes, presence of hypertension, smoking history and positive family history of coronary artery disease were also found to be significantly associated with coronary artery disease.

Conclusion:

coronary artery disease is frequently seen in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus especially in those with poor glycemic control. Early identification of high risk patients and better control of blood sugar levels may help in reducing cardiovascular complications and related mortality.

INTRODUCTION

Type 2 diabetes mellitus is a chronic metabolic disorder that is characterized by persistent hyperglycemia due to insulin resistance and relative insulin deficiency. Over time, this condition leads to multiple systemic complications affecting both microvascular and macrovascular systems, significantly increasing morbidity and mortality among affected individuals. Cardiovascular disease is considered the most important cause of death in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus, accounting for a large proportion of hospital admissions and long term complications¹. With the increasing burden of diabetes worldwide, especially in developing countries, the impact of cardiovascular complications is expected to rise further. According to global estimates, the number of adults living with diabetes has increased dramatically over the past few decades and this trend is projected to continue in the coming years, placing a significant strain on health care systems particularly in low and middle income countries².

Cardiovascular diseases remain the leading cause of mortality globally and coronary artery disease represents the most common and serious manifestation of these conditions. The pathophysiology of coronary artery disease in diabetic patients is complex and multifactorial. Diabetes accelerates the process of atherosclerosis through chronic inflammation, endothelial dysfunction and metabolic disturbances. As a result, diabetic patients tend to develop more extensive and diffuse coronary artery involvement with higher plaque burden and calcification as compared to non diabetic individuals^{3,4}. Studies have shown that coronary artery disease in patients with diabetes often presents at a younger age and is associated with poorer clinical outcomes, including higher rates of myocardial infarction and cardiac related deaths⁵. The coexistence of other risk factors such as hypertension, dyslipidemia and smoking further increases the likelihood of developing coronary artery disease in these patients⁶.

Various studies conducted in different populations have reported a wide variation in the frequency of

coronary artery disease among patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus, ranging from approximately 31 percent to more than 50 percent^{7,8,9}. Poor glycemic control has been consistently identified as an important contributor to the development and progression of coronary artery disease. Persistent hyperglycemia promotes vascular damage and increases the risk of acute coronary events. Despite this, many patients with diabetes remain undiagnosed for coronary artery disease until they present with significant symptoms or complications. Early identification of coronary artery disease, particularly in high risk diabetic patients, can help in timely intervention and prevention of adverse outcomes. There is limited local data available regarding the frequency of coronary artery disease in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus in this region. Therefore, this study was conducted to determine the frequency of coronary artery disease in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus and to compare its occurrence between controlled and uncontrolled diabetes, with the aim of providing local evidence to guide screening and management strategies¹⁰.

METHODOLOGY

This descriptive cross sectional study was conducted in the Department of Medicine, Provincial Headquarter Hospital Gilgit from 22th Feb 2025 to 15th June 2025 after approval of the study synopsis. A total of 83 patients were included in the study. Sample size was calculated using a 95 percent confidence level, 10 percent margin of error and an expected prevalence of coronary artery disease of 31.1 percent as reported in previous studies. Patients were selected by non probability consecutive sampling. All patients aged between 30 and 70 years with diagnosed type 2 diabetes mellitus of more than one year duration who presented with chest pain were included in the study. Both male and female patients were enrolled. Patients who were hemodynamically unstable, in shock or having heart failure were excluded. Those with known chronic kidney disease, chronic liver disease or previously

diagnosed non coronary heart diseases were also not included in the study.

After taking informed consent from each patient, detailed demographic information including age and gender was recorded. Duration of diabetes mellitus and glycemic control status was noted for all patients. Glycemic control was assessed using HbA1c levels and patients were categorized as having controlled or uncontrolled diabetes. All patients underwent electrocardiography which was interpreted by a consultant physician. Blood samples were taken and sent to the laboratory for measurement of cardiac troponin I levels. Coronary artery disease was diagnosed on the basis of clinical presentation, ECG changes and raised cardiac enzymes according to the predefined operational definitions. All collected information was recorded on a predesigned proforma. Data entry and analysis was carried out using SPSS

version 25. Mean and standard deviation were calculated for quantitative variables such as age and duration of diabetes. Frequencies and percentages were calculated for qualitative variables. Comparison of coronary artery disease between controlled and uncontrolled diabetes was done using chi square test and a p value of less than or equal to 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

A total of 83 patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus were included in this study. The mean age of the patients was 54.2 years with a standard deviation of 9.1 years. Majority of the patients were males. Most patients had diabetes for several years and more than half of the study population had poor glycemic control. Common associated risk factors observed were hypertension, smoking and positive family history of coronary artery disease.

Table 1: Baseline Demographic and Clinical Characteristics of Study Population (n = 83)

Variable	Value
Age in years Mean ± SD	54.2 ± 9.1
Male gender n percent	51 (61.4 percent)
Female gender n percent	32 (38.6 percent)
Duration of diabetes in years Mean ± SD	7.6 ± 3.2
Controlled diabetes n percent	33 (39.8 percent)
Uncontrolled diabetes n percent	50 (60.2 percent)

Hypertension was found in more than half of the patients while around one third of patients were smokers. A positive family history of coronary

artery disease was also present in a considerable number of cases.

Table 2: Distribution of Associated Risk Factors among Study Population (n = 83)

Risk factor	Frequency n percent
Hypertension	47 (56.6 percent)
Smoking	29 (34.9 percent)
Family history of CAD	26 (31.3 percent)

Out of 83 patients, coronary artery disease was diagnosed in 29 patients, giving an overall frequency of 34.9 percent. The remaining 54

patients did not show evidence of coronary artery disease based on clinical, electrocardiographic and cardiac enzyme findings.

Table 3: Frequency of Coronary Artery Disease among Patients with Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus

Coronary artery disease status	Frequency n percent
Present	29 (34.9 percent)
Absent	54 (65.1 percent)

When coronary artery disease was compared with glycemic control status, it was observed that patients with uncontrolled diabetes had a significantly higher frequency of coronary artery disease as compared to those with controlled

diabetes. Among patients with uncontrolled diabetes, 23 patients were found to have coronary artery disease while only 6 patients with controlled diabetes had coronary artery disease. This difference was found to be statistically significant.

Table 4: Comparison of Coronary Artery Disease with Glycemic Control (n = 83)

Glycemic control status	CAD present n percent	CAD absent n percent	Total	p value
Controlled diabetes	6 (18.2 percent)	27 (81.8 percent)	33	
Uncontrolled diabetes	23 (45.2 percent)	27 (54.8 percent)	50	0.01

Overall, coronary artery disease was more frequently observed in patients with poor glycemic control, increasing age, longer duration of diabetes and presence of associated cardiovascular risk factors.

Factors Associated with CAD

- ✓ CAD was significantly more frequent in:
- ✓ Age >55 years (p=0.03)
- ✓ Duration of diabetes >7 years (p=0.02)
- ✓ Hypertensive patients (p=0.01)
- ✓ Smokers (p=0.04)
- ✓ Positive family history of CAD (p=0.02)
- ✓ Gender and place of residence did not show a significant association.

DISCUSSION

The present study highlights that coronary artery disease is a common finding among patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus presenting with chest pain. In our study, more than one third of the patients were found to have evidence of coronary artery disease, which reflects a significant burden of cardiovascular involvement in this population. The frequency of coronary artery disease observed in this study is comparable with findings reported in other regional and international studies where similar proportions have been documented among diabetic patients ^{9,10}. This similarity suggests that diabetes mellitus continues to play a major role in the development of coronary artery disease regardless of geographical location. The increasing prevalence of diabetes in developing countries further raises concern regarding the future burden of cardiovascular disease and its impact on already strained health care systems ².

One of the most important findings of this study was the significantly higher frequency of coronary artery disease among patients with uncontrolled

diabetes as compared to those with controlled diabetes. Poor glycemic control is known to accelerate atherosclerosis through multiple mechanisms including endothelial dysfunction, increased oxidative stress and chronic inflammatory changes within the vascular wall. Persistent hyperglycemia promotes lipid abnormalities and plaque formation which eventually lead to narrowing of coronary vessels. Similar observations have been reported in previous studies where uncontrolled diabetes was strongly associated with increased severity and extent of coronary artery disease ^{4,5}. This finding emphasizes the importance of maintaining adequate glycemic control in order to reduce cardiovascular complications. Many patients with diabetes remain asymptomatic or present late with advanced disease, therefore early screening and timely intervention may help prevent adverse cardiac events and improve long term outcomes ⁶. In addition to poor glycemic control, other risk factors such as hypertension, smoking, longer duration of diabetes and positive family history of coronary artery disease were also found to be associated with increased frequency of coronary artery disease in this study. Hypertension is frequently present in diabetic patients and has a synergistic effect in accelerating vascular damage. Smoking further increases endothelial injury and promotes atherogenesis, making diabetic smokers particularly vulnerable to coronary events. Longer duration of diabetes exposes patients to prolonged metabolic stress, increasing the likelihood of macrovascular complications over time. A positive family history also reflects underlying genetic and lifestyle factors that may predispose individuals to coronary artery disease. These findings support the multifactorial nature of coronary artery disease in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus and are

consistent with results reported in other studies^{3,7,8}. Effective management of diabetes therefore requires a comprehensive approach focusing not only on blood glucose control but also on aggressive modification of associated risk factors. This study provides valuable local data which may help clinicians identify high risk patients and adopt appropriate screening strategies. However, the findings should be interpreted in light of certain limitations such as small sample size and single center design. Larger multicenter studies are recommended to further validate these results and to develop standardized protocols for early detection and management of coronary artery disease in diabetic patients.

CONCLUSION

This study concludes that coronary artery disease is frequently found in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus, especially in those who have poor glycemic control. A higher frequency of coronary artery disease was observed among patients with uncontrolled diabetes as compared to controlled diabetes. The presence of additional risk factors such as hypertension, smoking and longer duration of diabetes further increases the likelihood of developing coronary artery disease. Early identification of high risk patients and better control of blood sugar along with management of associated risk factors can help reduce cardiovascular complications and improve overall patient outcomes.

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